

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Organizational culture as a hybrid working-from-home environment two years after COVID-19

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Abstract

The COVID-19 epidemic has altered the nature of employment, with more individuals choosing to work from home. Many factors, including the demand for more work-life balance, the potential to save time on commutes, and the need for flexibility in the workplace, have contributed to the rise in popularity of hybrid work from home options. A Google questionnaire form was collected from 450 respondents from different sites to obtain the most accurate and current data. Monday is the most common day for employees to work from home if they are permitted to do so once a week. While working from home, the biggest problems are internet connectivity and technology devices unavailable at home. Those with further technological knowledge will be needed in the future when hiring. The majority of employees will take a 10% pay reduction from their present employer if it allows them to work from home. Work-from-home hybrid models are going to become the norm in the future. First preference when choosing a new company about 62.2% of employees choose the hybrid model of working from home. According to the survey, there is no set working hour while working from home, and there is also an excessive amount of work. According to the findings, 49.8% of respondents agree that having daily face-to-face interactions with coworkers or superiors is required and that these interactions are equally significant. The best option for freelancers in Patna will be to work from home because it has no impact on performance reviews or work-life balance. The survey recommended will assist HR managers, researchers, policymakers, and employers in better understanding the actions that need to be taken to ensure that hybrid workers working from home have a friendly work environment.

Keywords: Hybrid work-from-home; Survey Patna district; WFH; Telework; Post Covid-19

1. Introduction

Remote work has become the new standard. Following the COVID-19 epidemic, a significant number of employees were forcibly placed in situations they had never encountered before, providing a chance for both the employer and the employee to gain new experiences in the workplace. The COVID-19 epidemic has altered the nature of employment, with more individuals choosing to work from home. Many factors, including the demand for more work-life balance, the potential to save time on commutes, and the need for flexibility in the workplace, have contributed to the rise in popularity of work-from-home options. In addition to examining the status of hybrid work-from-home and the difficulties of working from home, this research paper will also examine how factors affect work conditions. Hybrid work models, which blend remote and in-office labour, have emerged as a result of the growth of working from home. This method preserves in-person interactions and team cohesion while providing the advantages of flexibility and remote work. The field of research on hybrid work-from-home, or blended work models, is fast developing, with fresh

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data and analysis coming in all the time following COVID-19. The pandemic has accelerated developments in the Future of Work, including as the development of hybrid models, increased emphasis on employee health benefits, and more workplace flexibility (Singh, Work from Home: It's Current Issues, Challenges and Opportunities, 2024).

2. Review of Literature

To lower exposure to the coronavirus and thereby reduce the risk of infection during the COVID-19 pandemic, a lot of office-based organisations advised and adopted work-from-home (WFH). (Casajus Valles, 2020). The experiment was conducted by Trip.com with the primary goal of determining the impact of hybrid work-from-home policies on employee attrition and job satisfaction (Nicholas Bloom R. H., 2024). The drawbacks of the hybrid work paradigm include the length of travel to and from the workplace, disruptions in the home or workplace, a lack of flexible work schedules, relocation, a dearth of employee involvement and training opportunities, burden, and work-life balance (S, 2023). The driving forces for the hybrid work paradigm include higher productivity, flexible home schedules, family time, and cooperation with coworkers when needed (S, 2023). The workplaces of the future could change significantly. Depending on the type of job, we may divide tasks into those that must be done at the office at home (Singh, WORK FROM HOME IS BECOMING THE NEW STANDARD OF EMPLOYMENT, 2024). In today's global market, companies that can adapt and modify working circumstances for their employees with flexibility will have a better chance of surviving and thriving (Adriana Grenčíková, 2024).

3. Research Methodology

Utilising Google Forms Primary data is gathered throughout the survey from September to December 2023. Because our respondents can easily grasp either English or Hindi, we gather data in both languages. Primary data was collected from total of 450 respondents. The snowball sampling method is done between September 2023 and December 2023. The survey was obtained from employees working in Patna District.

Research Objective

- To understand the Current situation of hybrid working from home model.
- Comparative analysis between work from home (WFH) and work from office (WFO)

Table 1 Primary Survey Details

Demographic Information about 450 respondents		
Sex	Male	67.6 %
	Female	32.4 %
Education Qualification	12th	8.23%
	Graduation	59.79%
	Post Graduation	25.56%
	Higher than post-Graduation	6.42%
Which Side of Patna Do You live?	East	22.9 %
	West	22%
	North	22.2 %
	South	14%
	Middle	16 %
	Near Patna	2.9%
Age	Below 20 Years	4%
	21 to 30 Years	34.5%
	31 to 40 Years	44.2%

	41 to 50 Years	14.2%
	Above 50 Years	3.1%
Yearly Income	Up to 300000	20.7 %
	300001 to 600000	22.2%
	600001 to 900000	37.3%
	900001 to 1200000	14.9%
	1200001 to 1500000	3.1%
	Above 1500001	1.8%

Figure 1 Daily travel from one side

From Fig. 1, based on data analysis on travels daily to reach your office, 42.9% travel up to 10 km; 36.4% travel 11 to 20 km; 13.1 % travel 21 to 30 km; 4.6% travel 31 to 40 km and 3% travel more than 40 km from one side. If we take the average travel by employee on one side to reach the office, it is 18.82 km, so from both sides it is 37.64 km. So, in the busy traffic of Patna city, it may take more than 2 hours of daily travel. It was found out that working from home saves money and time and reduces pollution from vehicles while travelling. There are numerous advantages to working from home, such as improved work-life balance, the ability to rise later, and the ability to work in your pyjamas, but avoiding the daily commute is undoubtedly one of the greatest benefits. The Bengaluru Outer Ring Road traffic is heavy as IT businesses raise the option for employees to work from home. Nearly every day, traffic on the Outer Ring Road is congested due to IT businesses' decision to reverse work-from-home directives and summon back staff (Balakrishna, 2023). While making more thoughtful and environmentally friendly traffic decisions will help reduce emissions and protect the environment for future generations, more remote job opportunities and flexible scheduling may be essential to bringing about that transformation (McCarthy, 2021). Working from home minimises the need for commuting, saving time and reducing tension (Singh, Analysing work from home after COVID-19 as the new normal, 2024). So with the hybrid model we reduced daily traffic and travel by 50 percent.

Based on the study of the data, 63.1% of respondents strongly agree, 22.7% agree, 6.9% are neutral, 3.8% disagree, and 3.6% greatly disagree that working from home is environmentally friendly. So, most of the respondents strongly agree that working from home is environmentally friendly. Taking the example of the Delhi government, which announced an odd-even scheme on November 6, 2023, to reduce pollution, if they announce the hybrid work-from-home model in all offices and schools, there will be an automatic change in the pollution level in Delhi. Work from home policies are supported by two or three organisations for environmental reasons, since fewer cars in the city mean less obstruction and air pollution (Dr. Kakhkashan Khan, 2022). (Figure 2)

Figure 2 comfortable environment

Figure 3 Status of different model

From Fig. 3, it is represented that 61.1% of respondents accepted work from home (WFH), 30.4% accepted hybrid work from home, and 8.4% accepted work from office (WFO) working models, able to manage work-life balance and fill less time during work. So still, employees of Patna accepted the work-from-home model the most, and hybrids came in second.

Figure 4 Knowledge of Work from home Apartment

From Fig. 4, according to the data analysis on listened about 1.5 BHK, 2.5 BHK, and 3.5 BHK apartments' concepts, 53.1% accepted no and 46.9% accepted yes.

Figure 5 Difficulty during Working from home

From Fig. 5 from the data analysis 36.2 % accepted Internet connectivity, 13.8 % accepted home working environments, and 11.3% accepted Less response from staff members; 24.9% accepted technology devices that are not available at home 8.2% accepted Not enough room to set up a home office and 5.6% accepted Miss office socialisation is one of the main factors employees encounter while working from home. Problems with connectivity and technology are the main challenges of working from home (singh, 2024). One potential consequence of working from home is a greater reliance on technology, which is prone to network problems and other technical difficulties. (Singh, Analysing work from home after COVID-19 as the new normal, 2024).

Figure 6 favorite Days of week

From Fig.6 from the data analysis 48.4% are in favor of Monday, 5.1% are in favor of Tuesday, 16.7% are in favor of Wednesday, 3.6% are in favor of Thursday, 13.3% are in favor of Friday and 12.9% are in favor of Saturday on the opinion that working from home is an option for an employee instead of the office day in a week. According to our data research, Monday is the most prevalent day in the Patna district. Wednesday is the second-most important day. Friday is the third, while Saturday is the least frequent day.

The most common day to work from home is Friday. Unexpectedly, Thursday comes next, and Monday comes third. The least popular WFH day is Wednesday (Nicholas Bloom J. M., 2024) For women respondents in the Patna district, Wednesday is the most common day, while Muslim respondents indicated that Friday is the most common day for certain activities. for them. Most of the women are working mothers, so they prefer Wednesday because the first two days' work, one day in the middle of the week, they work from home, and the next two to three days' work. The majority of Muslims support Friday because they worship Allah (the Almighty) on Friday from 12:30 to 2:00 pm and find that

working from home on Friday is beneficial. The majority of people who reside in 49 nations throughout the world are Muslims, so it will benefit them.

Figure 7 Preference During working from home

Based on the data analysis from Fig. 7, employee companies seem to favour some candidates over others during the recruitment process. Specifically, 76.4% of respondents preferred candidates with several years of work experience, and 23.6% preferred candidates with additional technology knowledge. Thus, it can be said that the corporation has begun to give preference to employees who are tech-savvy.

Figure 8 Offer during working from home

Based on data research from Fig. 8, employees responded that if their current company offers them a 10% lower salary and gives them a permanent or hybrid working home option, 60.9% say yes, 29.8% say maybe, and 9.3% say no, they accept that offer. The staff has taken to working from home since the Corona (Covid-19) pandemic. Even with an 18% pay decrease, American workers are willing to work remotely. They are not prepared to go to work at the office, even after receiving a raise in pay (Maurya, 2023).

Figure 9 Status Future Working model

Based on the data analysis of those surveyed, 57.8% strongly agree, 27.8% agree, 10.2% are neutral, 2.2% disagree, and 2% strongly disagree that work-from-home hybrid models are going to become the norm in the future. (Figure 9)

Figure 10 Preference During new company

Based on Figure 10, it shows that if an option is provided to an employee in choosing a new company, about 62.2% of them choose the hybrid model of work from home, 19.6% of them choose work from home, and 11.8% of them choose a 5% lower salary with the work from home option, 4.7% of them choose a 10% lower salary with the work from home option, and 1.8% of them choose a 10% to 20% lower salary with the work-from-home option. In the future, hybrid work-from-home models will be the best option for businesses (Arun, 2022). So it is concluded that hybrid work from home models will become the norm in the future.

Figure 11 Duration of hybride Work from home

Accepted the hybrid working approach or working from home Based on figure 11, it shows that 33.3% are working for more than 1 year, 26.2% are working for 6–12 months, 15.3% are working for 3-6 months, 14.9% are working for less than 3 months, and 10.2% are working for more than 2 years.

Figure 12 working Load

Based on data research from Fig. 12, 63.1% say there may be some time, 23.3% say yes, and 13.6% say not a single task is assigned to employees when they reach home while working from the office.

Figure 13 Time Duration

Based on data analysis, if there is no working time while working from home, 32% of respondents highly agree, 34.7% agree, 18% are neutral, 9.3% disagree, and 6% severely disagree. (Figure 13)

Figure 14 Working overload

Based on data analysis when it comes to the opinion that working from home results in an overflow of work, 16.7% of respondents highly agree, 36.5% agree, 28.6% are neutral, 12.8% disagree, and 5.4% strongly disagree. (Figure 14)

Figure 15 Electricity bill spending

Following data analysis 20.9% of respondents strongly agree, 24% agree, 43.6% are neutral, 7.3% disagree, and 4.2% greatly disagree that there is an increase in electric bills while working from home. (Figure 15). So, most of the respondents show a neutral response to the electricity bill.

Figure 16 Communication with Colleagues

Figure 16, shows that communicating with your colleagues or superiors is acceptable and that 49.8% connect Daily one-time, 35.8% connect Two times daily, 12.2% a few times per week, 1.6% connect once a week, and 0.7% connect Rarely when working from home.

Figure 17 Weightage of Face to Face Communication

When comparing face-to-face contact at work with communication from home, Figure 17 shows that 58.4% of the communication is equally effective, 36.4% is more effective, and 5.2% is less effective.

Figure 18 Work life balance

When asked if they have any trouble juggling work and life when they work from home, 43.8% of employees say they do, and 56.2% say they don't, according to data from a study shown in Figure 18. Hence, compared to working in an office, maintaining a work-life balance is easier while working from home.

Figure 19 Performance Appraisal

Based on data analysis regarding the impact of working from home on performance appraisals, 17.8% of respondents highly agree, 36.7% agree, 25.1% are indifferent, 15.6% disagree, and 4.9% severely disagree. (Figure 19). So, there is a mixed response from the respondent to the performance appraisal.

Figure 20 Option For Freelancers

As determined by data analysis, working from home is the best choice for freelancers in India, according to 40.4% of respondents who strongly agree with this statement, 33.8% who agree, 19.6% who are neutral, 4.9% who disagree, and 1.3% who strongly disagree. (Figure 20). The examination of the data indicates that freelancers will increasingly likely work from home in the future.

4. Result and Discussion

The most recent statistics and patterns indicate that both businesses and employees are favouring hybrid work-from-home arrangements. Numerous advantages come with hybrid work models, such as greater productivity, cost savings, lower carbon impact, and employee flexibility. But businesses must also deal with possible problems, including poor communication, technical glitches, and a diminished sense of corporate identity. Businesses may effectively adopt hybrid work arrangements that benefit employees and employers by giving remote workers the support they need. To go to their office, the majority of respondents travel up to 10 kilometers. With an average weight of 18.82 km and almost two hours of travel each day, working from home is a green option that may help maintain work-life balance and cut down on time spent on the job. The majority of workers are unaware of the 1.5, 2.5 BHK model, which was developed after home offices were established through work from home. Work from home (WFH) presents the most challenge,

Internet access was acknowledged by 36.6% of respondents. 24.9% said that electronic gadgets are unavailable for use at home. Monday is the preferred day for employees to work from home if they are allowed to select one day every week. In the future, the company's working style will be hybrid work-from-home (HWFH), and employees will be willing to accept a 10% pay reduction in exchange. Organisations are beginning to value employees with more technological expertise above those with more experience. Although employees will embrace a hybrid work paradigm, they will choose to work for the new firm. Employees acknowledged that they had adopted the hybrid work-from-home approach a year prior and that they may occasionally be assigned office responsibilities after they reach home. When working from home (WFH), there is no set work schedule, and working overtime is also possible. When working from home, there is no impact on the electricity cost. Most employees communicate once a day with their colleagues, and face-to-face communication is equally effective when working from home. There were no problems with work-life balance for the employee, and there was no impact on their performance reviews. Working from home as a freelancer is a fantastic opportunity. It is also fruitful for individuals who, even after the epidemic, have a prepared mindset to accept future working conditions as a hybrid work-from-home landscape.

5. Conclusion

The primary data is acquired from the employee regarding the existing situation of hybrid work-from-home models. This study will help HR managers, researchers, legislators, and employers better understand the activities that must be made to guarantee that hybrid workers working from home have a positive work environment.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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